
BROUGHT TO YOU BY ALEPH

BIOENGINEERED LIVING SYSTEMS WORKSHOP

The inaugural workshop for supporting agriculture in space.

4-5 DEC 2025

Mt Stromlo Observatory,
Australian National University

Australian
National
University

FOREWORD

Growing life beyond Earth starts with a question of profound consequences. What does it take for a living system to survive and grow when everything familiar is stripped away? Space agriculture is often framed as an engineering challenge, but at its heart it is a biological one. It invites us to think across scales, from molecules to organisms to entire habitats, and to recognise what must be understood and built to sustain life in extreme environments. Only by taking this whole-systems view can we clearly see the gap between what we can achieve today and what future missions will demand.

This workshop was convened to spotlight the pioneering work underway in Australia to harness plant science for space exploration, and to do three things together:

1. Clarify what today's technologies can and cannot yet do.
2. Imagine the next set of possibilities for sustainable plant systems beyond Earth.
3. Identify the knowledge gaps we must bridge to realise that future.

The program reflects this arc. We began by testing life, bringing phenomics and photobiology into conversation with the practical realities of measurement and performance in constrained environments. We then moved outwards to the resources that make life possible, focusing on water and nutrient supply and management, and what it means to find or design life for challenging environments. Day two carried the systems thinking further into engineering life support systems, before culminating in an explicit discussion of the knowledge gaps we must fill.

BIOENGINEERED LIVING SYSTEMS

Organisation committee

Chair

Professor Caitlin Byrt

Committee member

Dr Yeorgia Argirou

Committee member

Pip Wilkes

Committee member

Zhou Yi Wang

BIOENGINEERED LIVING SYSTEMS

Acknowledgement

We gratefully acknowledge the speakers, panellists and attendees who contributed their time, expertise and thoughtful discussions to the 2025 Bioengineered Living Systems Workshop. We further acknowledge the support of:

- **The Australian Space Agency** for funding support via the Moon to Mars Initiative.
- **Australian Plant Phenomics Network** and **ANU Agrifood Innovation Institute** team members for support.
- **Dr Cecile Gueidan** for the Lichen Tour organisation.
- **Richard Poire** (phenomics/photobiology), **Graham Dorrington** (engineering life support systems) and **Lauren Fell** (knowledge gap panel) for session organisation.

BIOENGINEERED LIVING SYSTEMS

2025 PROGRAM

4th December | Common Room, Mt Stromlo Observatory

Coffee and speed introductions

9:30 AM

Official welcome by Caitlin Byrt

10:00 AM

Introduction to Lunaria One by Lauren Fell

10:40 AM

Session 1

Testing life: phenomics and photobiology

Session introduction by Richard Poire

10:40-10:50 AM

Presentation by Owen Atkin

10:50-11:10 AM

Presentation by Cheryl McCarty

11:10-11:30 AM

Presentation by Brett Williams

11:30-11:50 AM

Presentation by Jordan Gemmel

11:50-12:00 noon

Lunch

12:00-1:00 PM

Session 2

Finding and designing life for challenging environments & supporting life: water and nutrient resource supply and management

Lichen tour by Cecile Gueidan

1:00-1:30 PM

Presentation by Stefania Peracchi

1:30-1:45 PM

Presentation by Tien Huynh

1:45-2:00 PM

Presentation by Natasha Disha

2:00-2:15 PM

Afternoon tea

2:15-3:00 PM

Workshop activities

3:00-5:00 PM

Activity 1: building future capacity

Activity 2: future scanning

BIOENGINEERED LIVING SYSTEMS

2025 PROGRAM

5th December | Common Room, Mt Stromlo Observatory

Coffee and speed introductions

9:30 AM

Presentation by Allen Wen

9:50-10:05 AM

Session 3

Engineering life support systems

Session introduction by Graham Dorrington

10:05-10:20 AM

Presentation by Volker Hessel

10:30-10:50 AM

Presentation by William Hollier

10:50-11:20 AM

Presentation by Tom Loan

11:20-12:00 NOON

Lunch

12:00-1:00 PM

Presentation by Ming-Dao Chia

1:00-1:20 PM

Presentation by Shagufta Iqbal

1:20-1:40 PM

Session 4

Knowledge gaps we need to fill

Panel with Lauren Fell and Sharon Robinson

1:40-3:00 PM

Gelato break

3:00 PM

Conference dinner

5:30 PM

THE DAY IN REVIEW

Testing life: phenomics and photobiology

Lichen tour

THE DAY IN REVIEW

Engineering life support systems

Messina break

Invited speaker: Lauren Fell (Lunaria One)

Welcome address to the ALEPH Workshop

Biography

Lauren Fell is the founder and mission lead of Lunaria One's Australian Lunar Experiment Promoting Horticulture (ALEPH), an initiative preparing to send carefully selected seeds and resurrection plants to the lunar surface to test whether germination and early growth are possible beyond Earth. Through ALEPH, she brings together scientists, engineers, and specialists to advance a future where resilient plant systems support space exploration, while also building strong outreach and citizen science engagement. Alongside this work, Lauren is a PhD researcher in Quantum Cognition at the Queensland University of Technology (QUT), where she studies human decision-making and trust in complex environments, including off-Earth habitation contexts. She has also been recognised through multiple NASA innovation design challenges for space-focused concept development.

Plants on the Moon

Lunaria

www.plantsonthemoon.au

Invited speaker: Richard Poiré (ANU)

Session introduction to “Testing Life: Phenomics and Photobiology”

Biography

Dr Richard Poiré is a plant ecophysiologicalist and phenomics specialist with extensive experience designing and applying high-throughput plant phenotyping tools in controlled environments. Trained in France and Germany, his early work combined modelling and image-based approaches to understand how light and temperature shape plant growth and photosynthetic performance across diverse species. Richard has held research and training roles across major international and Australian institutions, including CSIRO and IRRI, supporting plant phenomics capability and platform development. He is currently based at The Australian National University (ANU), where he supports access to advanced plant growth and phenotyping infrastructure and applies hyperspectral imaging and deep learning to develop scalable proxies for key physiological traits.

Testing life: Phenomics and Photobiology session

Dr Richard Poiré

Australia is a world leader in plant phenomics

APPN Overview

➤ APPN Head Office (UoA)

➤ 9 Nodes:

- Australian National University
- Charles Sturt University
- Department of Primary Industries & Regional Development, WA
- La Trobe University
- University of Adelaide
- University of Queensland
- University of Sydney
- University of Western Australia
- Wester Sydney University

Mobile phenotyping		
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phenotyping

Plant growth facilities

Controlled Environment (C.E.) chambers

CEWalk-in rooms

Greenhouses of various sizes

Whole tree chambers

PC2 and quarantine facilities

Phenotyping platforms

Plant-to-sensor platforms (e.g. HTP Smarthouses, X-ray CT Scanner)

Sensor-to-plant technologies (e.g. XY system in large C.E. Room, various handheld devices, portable hyperspec scanner)

Gravimetric systems

DroughtSpotter platforms inside-by-side C.E.R.s to support heat/drought studies

DroughtSpotter system in greenhouse

Root phenotyping

Various systems (Rhizoboxes, Rhizolysimeter, X-ray CT Scanner, mini Rhizotron)

3D scanners at APPN-ANU:

- 3 x 3D Scanners available
 - 2 x Multispec capability
- Suitable for plants with varying heights (up to 1.2 m)
- Outputs:
 - Point Clouds
 - .csv files with numeric data

APPN-ANU Services: 3D-multispec scanning

Can cold atmospheric plasma make water enriched with minerals from Martian or Lunar regolith more suitable for hydroponic plant growth?

Syamlal Sasi^a, Priyanka Prakash^b, Richard Poiré^b, Tao Hu^b, Janith Weerasinghe^c, Igor Levchenko^{c,d}, Karthika Prasad^{b,e}, Katia Alexander^{b,e}

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:
Lunar
Martian
Soil simulants
Hydroponics
Cold atmospheric plasma

ABSTRACT

In space agriculture, a soil-free cultivation method with low system complexity and mass, hydroponics offers passive aeration, automation, and a means to overcome inefficient distribution of water and limited convective mixing of substrate-based growth systems under micro- and low gravity conditions. Incorporation of local regolith into the hydroponics system has been considered as a step towards *in situ* resource utilisation, however previous studies demonstrated reduced growth and stress morphologies in plants grown in regolith. This study explores whether cold atmospheric plasma (CAP) treatment can be used to improve the quality of water enriched with regolith particles, and thus enhance the growth, yield and vitality of microgreens. CAP treatment of Simulated Martian Regolith (W-SMR) water for 10 or 30 min increased shoot length of *Brassica oleracea* by 11.4% and 89%, and *Medicago sativa* by 218% and 195%, respectively. For Simulated Lunar Regolith (W-SLR), CAP treatment increased shoot length of *M. sativa* by 113% and 88%, and *B. oleracea* by 108% and 129%. Root length also increased, notably for *M. sativa* in W-SLR and *B. oleracea* in W-SMR, with smaller effects for *M. sativa* in W-SMR. CAP treatment was found to alter the concentration of essential elements known to affect plant development, increasing the concentrations of ²⁴Mg, ³¹P, ³⁹K, ⁶⁶Zn, and ¹³⁶Ce known to promote plant growth, while reducing the concentrations of ²³V and ²⁷Al that may be responsible for a greater level of stress in plants grown in untreated solutions due to their influence on enzymatic processes. These results confirm the potential of CAP treatment to improve productivity of hydroponic systems that utilise local regolith as an alternative to closed loop systems.

Enhanced Plant Growth on Simulated Martian Regolith via Water Chemistry Optimisation: The Role of RONS and Nano/Micro-Bubbles

Syamlal Sasi^a, Priyanka Prakash^b, Steve Hayden^c, David Dooley^c, Richard Poiré^b, Tao Hu^b, Janith Weerasinghe^d, Igor Levchenko^e, Karthika Prasad^{b,e} and Katia Alexander^{b,e}*

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Abstract

Development of sustainable agriculture on Mars is a critical step towards its colonisation. However, Martian regolith is coarse-grained, and its mineral profile differs significantly from that of terrestrial arable soil, resulting in poor seed germination success and stunted plant development. This study investigates whether germination success and plant growth can be improved by exposing seeds and plants to water enriched with either i) biochemically active reactive oxygen and nitrogen species generated by atmospheric pressure plasma (APW) or ii) nano-/micro-bubbles and minerals such as potassium and calcium extracted from Aquapulse® feldspar (APW), a type of rock that is readily available on Mars, at different stages of the crop lifecycle. As a crop model, microgreen crops of *B. oleracea* and *M. sativa* are chosen for their short growth cycle, low resource requirements, and high nutritional value. For *B. oleracea* crops, soaking of seeds in PAW followed by irrigation with APW led to an increase in germination by ~566.7%, in biomass by 412.4%, and in chlorophyll content by 17.7% compared to crops grown using normal water for seed soaking and irrigation. For *M. sativa* crops, the use of APW for soaking and irrigation yielded an increase of 41.7% in seed germination and 45.2% in crop biomass, whereas the use of PAW for both soaking and irrigation resulted in the greatest improvement in seed germination, 41.7%, when compared to control. These results suggest that, with further optimisation, a regimen of treatment with PAW and APW in place of normal water can be used to address stage-specific challenges of the crop lifecycle in Martian regolith. As amending Martian regolith with a minimum of 1% organic matter is required to promote healthy plant development, further studies should investigate the use of plasma-mediated reforming of biowaste for *in situ* production of e.g., biochar.

Keywords: simulated Martian regolith; nano-/micro-bubbles; cold atmospheric plasma

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Fig. 6. Area analysis of leaves harvested from *M. sativa* and *B. oleracea* after 40 sols of hydroponic cultivation in W-SMR, and W-SLR as a function of the length of time the water is treated with CAP (a-d). (e-h) Images of leaves during leaf area analysis. (e-f) Images of *M. sativa* leaves grown in (e) W-SLR and (f) PT30-W-SLR. (g-h) Images of *B. oleracea* leaves grown in (g) W-SMR and (h) PT30-W-SMR. *** represent statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) difference among groups.

Wheat Physiology Predictor

LMA
N area
SPAD
N mass
Vc max
Vc max25
J
Photosynthesis
s
Cond
Vcmax25/Narea

Predict wheat physiology

- **Measure hyperspectral reflectance using the ASD FieldSpec Spectroradiometer**
This quick and easy measurement can be done in the lab or in the field.
- **Upload your data**
Simply upload raw, CSV-formatted data straight from the FieldSpec. Your data will automatically be corrected for breaks between detectors.
[Download a sample data file](#)

Viri Silva Perez

Wheat Physiology Predictor

Wheat Physiology Predictor

<https://plantpredict.shinyapps.io/PredictionShiny/>

<https://plantmethods.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s13007-021-00806-6>

Physiological traits such as V_{cmax25} , N_{area} , J , etc.

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Testing life: Phenomics and Photobiology session

Prof. Owen Atkin (ANU)
A/Prof. Cheryl McCarty (UniSQ)
A/Prof. Brett Williams (QUT)

Contact Us

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We are proudly supported by

APPN plant phenotyping infrastructure and expertise is strategically located at nine locations across Australia:

APPN-ANU Services: Controlled Environments

Plant Growth Facility (PC2):

- Quarantine approved
- 31 reach-in growth chambers in the PGF
 - Three-tier and single tier chambers
 - Range: +4 to +40°C; and -10 to +40 °C
 - Dynamic climate control

Eucalyptus Glasshouse (PC2):

- Six growing rooms
- Elevated CO₂ capability
- Two PC2 lab spaces
- 3D scanner

Non-PC2:

- 8 x Outdoor Growth chambers
 - 2 x High light capability
 - 2 x Multispectral lighting
 - 2 x 3D scanners
 - Elevated CO₂ capability

APPN-ANU Services: Equipment hire

Modality	Specs	Traits / Features
Hyperspectral reflectance	Leaf ASD or SVC 350-2500nm	hyperspectral reflectance
	Canopy 350-1000nm Canopy 350-1700nm	
Multispec	RGB-NIR 3D Phenospex traitfinder dualscan canopy scanners (3)	morphological and spectral traits (14+) Chlorophyll content
	Leaf Chlorophyll content (CCM300) Imaging Walz Hexagon	
Fluorescence	Licor 600 porometer /fluo	PAM parameters on small plants and crops
	Plant Explorer Pro (top and side view for tall crops (coming end of 2025))	
Thermal IR	FLIR T645 and FLIR A645	Canopy temperature
RGB	Mavic M3M Drone RGB NIR	Fractional cover, height, vegetative indices
Gas exchange	Licor 6800 / 6400 portable photosynthesis systems	Photosynthesis rate
		Respiration

Invited speaker: Owen Atkin (ANU)

Talk title:

Biography

Professor Owen Atkin is a plant scientist at The Australian National University (ANU) and Director of the ANU Agrifood Innovation Institute, where he leads interdisciplinary efforts spanning biological and environmental sciences, engineering, data science, and policy to address complex challenges facing the agrifood sector. Trained at ANU and the University of Toronto, and with academic experience in the UK at the University of York, he has built a career investigating how environmental gradients shape plant physiology, with a particular focus on respiration, temperature responses, and the resilience of leaf carbon metabolism. His research integrates field surveys, physiological and biochemical studies, and collaboration with modelling groups to improve how plant respiration is represented in larger-scale biosphere and climate models. Professor Atkin has served as an Editor for *New Phytologist* since 2007 and has held leadership roles across major national plant research initiatives, including the ARC Centre of Excellence for Plant Energy Biology.

Invited speaker: Cheryl McCarty (UniSQ)

Talk title: Machine vision sensing of plant health

Biography

Associate Professor Cheryl McCarthy is a mechatronic engineer with the Centre for Agricultural Engineering at the University of Southern Queensland (UniSQ). Her research focuses on developing machine vision and sensing systems for agriculture, spanning both crop and livestock applications. She has led and contributed to projects using imaging and artificial intelligence to support welfare monitoring in poultry production, as well as precision sensing approaches across multiple agricultural industries. More recently, Associate Professor McCarthy has played a leading role in advancing Australian capability in autonomous plant growth monitoring for space, including the development of machine vision techniques for early detection of plant stress and performance in controlled environments. Her work bridges engineering and biology to enable scalable, data-driven plant monitoring technologies with impact for both space-based food production and resilient agriculture on Earth.

University of
Southern
Queensland

Machine vision sensing of plant health

Terrestrial and space agriculture

A/Prof Cheryl McCarthy
cheryl.mccarthy@unisq.edu.au

Centre for Agricultural Engineering

UniSQ Centre for Agricultural Engineering

- Automation in crop protection, biosecurity, livestock monitoring, harvesting and post harvest processing
 - Autonomous machinery: tractors, harvesters, irrigation machines, drones
 - Spray nozzles, drafting pens, machine path planning
- Software, electronics, mechanisms, sensing, control, algorithms

Sensing and automation in terrestrial farming environments

- Remote
- Limited power and connectivity
- Limited humans onsite
- Many site configurations and conditions
- Many plant varieties
- Optimise resources

Moon to Mars Demonstrator – Early detection of plant stress

Deep space missions require onboard food production (e.g. plants) rather than resupply

Current plant habitats

Machinevision monitoring

Automated health reports

Veggie and Advanced Plant Habitat onboard ISS
Source: NASA

Moon to Mars Demonstrator – Early detection of plant stress

Day 15

Some plants need attention ★ ★ ★

Controlled Environment Agriculture

ASA Moon to Mars Demonstrator 2021-2022

Novel machine vision has greater sensitivity at low cost

UKSA / ASA International Bilateral Fund Phase 2

- Multi-site plant experiments with machine vision
 - RaspberryPi, different camera angles
- Engineering Development Unit for middeck locker

Crossover applications in vertical farming

Salt stress applied to front tray – health signal drops (orange boxes) before visual signs

Plant health monitoring payload on ISS

Aim: Machine vision detection of plant stress in microgravity conditions, with applications in terrestrial farming

Payload comprises a small terrarium with lettuce seeds

- 250 mL capacity
- Two payloads on mission

Hermetically sealed in two 2U CubeLabs

- Each 20 cm 10 cm 10 cm

4-week mission on ISS

- From seeds to ~6 true leaves
- Nutrient-rich agar substrate
- Camera monitoring

Ground testing of plant chamber design for microgravity

Nutrient agar in tub, no fan

Nutrient agar in tray, 3 mm holes & plugs

Vermiculite & perlite in tray, geotextile cover

Nutrient agar in tub, with fan at Day 30 (for visual comparison)

Nutrient agar in tub, with fan 10 min/h

Nutrient agar in tray, 10 mm holes

Sphagnum moss & vermiculite in tray

Nutrient agar & vermiculite in tray

- Fans on some of the time better than always on or always off
- Larger plant growth stage shown at top right of slide

- Agar needs air exchange within biochamber (e.g. larger diameter germination holes)
- Largest plant growth stage shown

- Other substrates with more aeration can sustain larger plants than agar in tray, but less than agar in tub
- Largest plant growth stage shown

- Agar with vermiculite for aeration
- Largest plant growth stage shown

Invited speaker: Brett Williams (QUT)

Talk title: Desiccation strategies of *Tripogon loliiformis*

Biography

Associate Professor Brett Williams is a research group leader and Senior Lecturer in Plant Science at Queensland University of Technology (QUT), and a Vice Chancellor's Research Fellow in the Centre for Tropical and Biocommodities. His research investigates how plants regulate programmed cell death, senescence, and energy metabolism under stress, with a particular focus on naturally resilient species such as the Australian resurrection grass *Tripogon loliiformis*. After completing his BS and PhD at QUT, Dr Williams undertook research at Texas A&M University, studying plant cell death responses to biotic and abiotic stimuli. He now leads projects aimed at translating fundamental discoveries into improved crop performance, including work on stress tolerance in pulses such as chickpea. His research combines molecular biology and next-generation transcriptomics to better understand how plants survive extreme environments and how these mechanisms can be harnessed for agriculture in challenging conditions.

A close-up photograph of a person's hand holding a small clump of reddish-brown soil. A small, dry, spiky plant is growing from the soil. The background is a blurred, reddish-brown landscape, likely a dry, arid environment. The text "Desiccation Strategies of Tripogon loliiformis" is overlaid on the image in white font.

Desiccation Strategies of *Tripogon loliiformis*

Drought and desiccation tolerance

Desiccation tolerance
Waterlosstoair-drylevel and recover normal functiononrehydration

*Relative water content(RWC)

What is a resurrection plant?

- Typically found on rocky outcrops in tropical and sub-tropical climates
- Capable of being restored from a dry and seemingly moribund state (RWC 1 %)
- Two types
 - True desiccation plants (non vascular)
 - □ Lichens, ferns mosses
- Modified desiccation tolerant plants (angiosperms)

Tripogon loliiformis, a Native Australian Resurrection Plant

- Tolerates Desiccation <5% RWC
- Fast-growing and relatively easy to grow in the lab
- Recovers within 24-72h
- Widespread throughout Australia
- Family Poaceae (True Cereals)
- Diploid ($2n = 20$)

Tripogon Drying Curve

Tripogon retains its chlorophyll during desiccation

Chlorophyll integrity

Chlorophyll florescence

CO₂ assimilation rate

Internal structure

Leaf folding

Middle of the leaf

Base of the leaf

FLIR

Thermal Imaging at the AFFP

Photon Systems
Instrument

Photon System Instrument (PSI)

	Size (pixel)	F0	Fm	YII (Φ_{PSII})
Area 1	6083	13.69	118.79	0.88
Area 2	2117	19.35	118.17	0.84
Area 3	332	14.90	63.66	0.77
Area 4	222	19.64	52.86	0.63

Transcriptome Analysis of Drying and Desiccated *Tripogon loliiformis*

Collected samples from Charleville

Resurrect samples and perform dehydration treatments in the lab

Harvest RNA from critical hydration points

High Throughput Sequence

De novo Transcriptome Assembly

Expression and Other Downstream Analyses

T.loliiformis "PCDome"

	Shoots			Roots				
	60%	40% < 10%	Rehyd	60%	40% < 10%	Rehyd		
Death (Pro-apoptotic)								
Metacaspase-1-like	-111.5	-228	-227	-1.61	-130.1	-452.8	-445.3	-1.02
Metacaspase-4-like	-9.4	-6.71	-15.67	3.24	-7.13	-33.27	-17.14	1.29
E3 ubiquitin-protein ligase AIP2-like	-4.68	-5	-3.94	3.25	-1.94	-1.29	-3.33	1.06
Death-inducer obliterator 1-like	-4.67	-8.29	-2.64	1.07	-3.68	-3.81	-3.76	-1.11
Aspartic Protease Asp-1	-26.62	-14.23	-45.89	-9.63	-18.68	-120.6	-346	-1.41
Survival (Anti-apoptotic)								
Transmembrane BAX inhibitor motif-containing protein 4	10.67	10.4	9.86	1.57	6.83	6.76	10.15	1.92
Inhibitor of apoptosis-like protein	3.62	3	1.18	1.55	-1.57	-2.84	-2.24	1.57
Inhibitor of Apoptosis (IAP)	10.33	4.5	1	5.33	3.21	2.51	-1.33	2.68
Aging (Senescence)								
Inducers of Senescence								
Protein SRG1	-30.28	-50.17	-20.61	-1.66	-16.33	-8.17	-3.43	-1.19
Protein SRG1	-17.59	-16.51	-7.05	-8	-2.67	1.38	2.13	-4.5
Senescence-associated protein DH	-7.24	-2.53	-3.76	-4.56	-20.09	-38.89	-62.27	-1.04
Putative senescence-associated protein	-23.45	-44.17	-263	-1.91	-2.36	-3.18	-4.33	1.8
Delay of Senescence								
Protein Delay of the onset of senescence	2.03	2.02	-1.16	-2.84	2.51	2.33	2.04	-1.37
Survival and Youth (Autophagy)								
ATG4	2.32	2.55	2.39	-1.15	1.24	1.13	-1.26	-1.05
ATG7	3.15	4.62	8.72	1.09	-1.67	-1.43	-2.04	-2.72
ATG9	2.12	2.94	2.85	1.31	1.65	1.66	1.85	1.37

Autophagy triggered in dehydrating and desiccated *T. loliiformis* tissues

Williams B, Njaci L, Moghaddam L, Long H, Dickman MB, et al. (2015) Trehalose Accumulation Triggers Autophagy during Plant Desiccation. *PLoS Genet* 11(12): e1005705. doi:10.1371/journal.pgen.1005705

<http://journals.plos.org/plosgenetics/article?id=info:doi/10.1371/journal.pgen.1005705>

Trehalose accumulation correlates with drying and the onset of autophagy

Trehalose induces autophagy in hydrated leaves

Summary

- Tripogon tolerates desiccation during gradual but not rapid drying
- Homochlorophyllous plant that retains ~70 % of its chlorophyll
- Shuts down photosynthesis early
- Undergoes substantial structural changes (leaf folding and rolling during dehydration)
- Structural changes are visible within 24 hrs of watering
- Photosynthesis can be measured within 24 hrs of watering

Invited speaker: Cecile Gueidan (CSIRO)

Guided lichen tour around the Mt Stromlo Observatory

Biography

Dr Cécile Gueidan is a Senior Researcher at the Australian National Herbarium (CSIRO), where she studies the systematics and evolution of lichenised fungi and other ascomycete lineages. Her research combines morphological and molecular approaches, including molecular phylogenetics and emerging high-throughput herbarium genomics, to understand biodiversity, trait evolution, and the origins of symbiosis in fungal groups that inhabit some of Earth's most challenging environments. Dr Gueidan's work has focused extensively on the lichen family Verrucariaceae, as well as rock-inhabiting and black yeast-like fungi, and she is increasingly interested in Australian lichens and biological soil crust ecosystems. Trained in France and the United States, she has held research positions in the Netherlands and the United Kingdom before joining CSIRO in Australia. Her work highlights how resilient symbiotic systems evolve and persist under extreme constraints, offering valuable insight into the biological foundations of life in harsh environments.

Invited speaker: Stefania Peracchi (ANSTO Centre for Accelerator Science)

Talk title: Space radiobiology at ANSTO

Biography

Dr Stefania Peracchi is a nuclear physicist and Irradiations Team Lead at ANSTO's Centre for Accelerator Science (CAS), where she leads precision ion beam irradiation programs for studying space radiation effects on electronics, advanced materials, and biological systems. Her work draws on expertise in space radiation environments, microdosimetry, radiation protection, and shielding, supported by accelerator facilities that enable mission-relevant simulation of proton and heavy-ion exposure. Dr Peracchi's research spans both space science and radiobiology, with applications ranging from qualification of spacecraft technologies to radiation medicine. As a space radiation expert, she has contributed to national capability-building initiatives, including efforts to expand Australia's space radiation testing network. Dr Peracchi is also an official partner of the ALEPH project, supporting radiation exposure testing of seeds and resilient biological samples to assess survivability and performance under conditions relevant to lunar missions and long-duration spaceflight.

Space

Radiobiology at

ANSTO

Dr Stefania Peracchi
Centre for Accelerator Science
Irradiations Team Lead

Science. Ingenuity. Sustainability.

Space radiation and its challenges

ANSTO Space Radiation Hub

Radiation Facilities:

Centre for Accelerator Science & Heavy Ions GATRI	(Cobalt 60) Gamma rays
Australian Synchrotron	X-rays
Australian Centre for Neutron Scattering	Neutrons

Testing of:

- Electronics
- Materials
- Biological matter

ANSTO supports Industry and Academia

- via merit-based schemes supported by the Australian Government under the National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy
- via commercial rapid response scheme to protect proprietary information

Centre for Accelerator Science & GATRI

Sydney

Australian Synchrotron

Melbourne

The Universe in a tank

PARTICLES ACCELERATOR

Any possible ion
in space can be
produced.
Mimic fluxes and
dose typical of
different orbits
& missions.

Ion Precision Irradiation

- ✓ Irradiation of biological and soft matter (cells, organoids, animals, seeds, plants, food etc..)
- ✓ Dose rates typical of space.
- ✓ On-site complementary radiobiology PC1 and PC2 laboratories for pre- and post-irradiation sample handling, including, green house and animal house.

CASE STUDY

ALEPH-1: Growing Plant On The Moon

Artistic Impression ©
G. E Dorrington & Georgelas, RMIT, April 2025

Fundamental Radiobiology

Simplest animal ON EARTH

Trichoplax

Insights for space biology, human health, and the evolutionary impact of ionizing radiation.

Most complex animal ON EARTH

Human

Human DNA breaks and Repair Mechanism

Geant4-DNA modelling

- Full human fibroblast geometry implemented based on molecularDNA example⁸

Experimental Measurement of breaks and repairs

speracch@ansto.gov.au

Australian Government

Invited speaker: Tien Huynh (RMIT)

Talk title: The effect of high altitude on plants, bacteria and fungi (delivered digitally)

Biography

Associate Professor Tien Huynh is a multidisciplinary researcher and educator whose work is driven by a commitment to environmental sustainability, health and wellbeing, and equity for disadvantaged communities. She completed her PhD at the University of Melbourne and undertook postdoctoral research in the UK and Italy, specialising in evolutionary phylogenetics and conservation biology, before expanding into biomedical research spanning cancer biology, tissue repair, neuropharmacology, and drug discovery technologies. Her expertise now bridges biotechnology, medical science, mycology, manufacturing, and advanced materials engineering. Dr Huynh is also a recognised science communicator and has been featured widely across global media. In recognition of her leadership and impact, she was awarded Superstars of STEM by Science & Technology Australia. Through her teaching and outreach, she fosters a culture of curiosity and collaboration, and supports students to apply science in real-world contexts through industry engagement and international programs.

Invited speaker: Natasha Disha (ANU)

Talk title: Zero-G manufacturing CRC bid details

Biography

Natasha Disha is a strategic projects and space-sector professional based at the ANU Institute for Space (InSpace), where she serves as Manager of Strategic Projects and Bid Lead for the Future of Space Cooperative Research Centre (Sustainable Space Technology Pillar). Her work focuses on building collaborations and delivering large, mission-driven initiatives at the intersection of research, industry, and national capability development. Natasha has experience across engineering, systems thinking, and automation-enabled project delivery, with prior roles at The Australian National University including analyst and software automation development. She holds a Bachelor of Engineering (Honours) and Bachelor of Science (Honours) from ANU and has undertaken professional leadership training through the University of Oxford's Leading Strategic Projects Programme.

ZERO-G

Manufacturing

CRC Bid Details

Space.CRCBid@anu.edu.au

ZERO-G Manufacturing CRC bid - ANU InSpace

The ZERO-G Manufacturing (CRC) is a pioneering \$100 million, 10-year initiative aimed at accelerating the development of a sustainable, multi-billion-dollar space-enabled manufacturing economy in Australia. By leveraging routine access to and return from space, the CRC seeks to position Australia as a global leader in sustainable space-based innovation and advanced manufacturing.

Australia's space manufacturing opportunity directly addresses key industry painpoints—cost, scalability, innovation, and sustainability. By investing now, businesses gain access to advanced platforms, safe re-entry logistics, and inclusive innovation frameworks—positioning them to lead in a competitive, future-facing economy.

The ACT and Canberra will take the lead in developing Australia's microgravity manufacturing ecosystem, driving innovation and production in this emerging field.

Access to the low gravity environment can enable new and improved products to be manufactured without defects created by Earth's gravity. These sectors positively impacted include:

Pharmaceuticals and Life Sciences

Tissue Engineering & Biotech

Semiconductors

Photonics

Advanced Materials

Microfluidics and Biofilms

The cost of access to and from space has always been the limiting factor in the development of a space manufacturing ecosystem that can deliver societal-level impact on the ground. However, the technology is rapidly catching up and Australia has been identified as a potential first mover:

Varda's "W-3" capsule parachutes down to the Kooniba Test range in South Australia (Southern Launch Australia)

Intuitive Machines are developing large payload (100kg) capacity able to land safely within 50m of any target area (e.g. CBR airport)

The ZERO-G Manufacturing CRC brings together partners across research, industry, government and communities to accelerate a holistic space-manufacturing ecosystem. The CRC will focus on fostering cross-sector innovation, bringing together the space-enabling sector with end-users across adjacent sectors and regional communities.

The Future of Space CRC will achieve its vision through four integrated research programs:

Program 1: Accelerate commercialisation pipelines	Program 2: Advance Manufacturing Innovation	Program 3: Enable Safe and Sustainable Re-entry	Program 4: Foster Social Licence and Inclusion
<p>Expand and mature a pipeline of product business cases to lay the foundation for a thriving space-enabled economy. Targeting adjacent sectors including pharmaceuticals, life sciences, optical technologies, advanced materials and Defence.</p>	<p>Develop novel materials, platforms and componentry to meet the evolving needs of business cases developed in Program 1 and beyond. Design and test capability such as automation, robotics and in situ monitoring to enable in-space manufacturing.</p>	<p>Enable routine and reliable return from space. Accelerate advanced simulation, detection, and recovery technologies to ensure that Australia can safely retrieve manufactured goods and scientific payloads.</p>	<p>Co-create an ecosystem that ensures the active participation and embedded knowledge of First Nations communities in the space-enabled economy. Ensure social responsibility, national alignment and long-term sustainability.</p>

Developing future talent: A skilled workforce is the backbone of any advanced industry. The Future of Space CRC's education and workforce development program ensures that Australia has the talent pipeline needed to deliver on its research agenda and sustain growth in the space-enabled manufacturing sector for decades to come.

- The funding term of the ZERO-G Manufacturing Cooperative Research Centre is ten years.
- The target cash funding is AUD 100 million (consisting of AUD 50 million in Commonwealth Grant funding through the Cooperative Research Centre Program and AUD 50 million from across the partners of ZERO-G Manufacturing CRC). This target cash funding is in addition to the target in-kind contributions equivalent to AUD 80 million to be sought from both university and non-university partners.
- The above-mentioned funding amounts will be used to fund the Cooperative Research Centre’s activities over the course of the ten-year funding term.

Total Amount Over 10 Years

- NT
- Remote infrastructure

WA **Curtin University**

- Re-entry detection
- Space sustainability

SA **Adelaide University**

- Re-entry, growing commercial space port
- Growing pharmaceutical precinct

- TAS
- Tobe developed

- QLD
- Launch
 - Infrastructure – regional data centre hub

NSW **MACQUARIE University SYDNEY AUSTRALIA**

- Resilient componentry
- Advanced manufacturing
- Business, policy and governance

ACT **Australian National University**

- Precision re-entry from space
- Pharmaceutical distributions
- Indigenous health

VIC **SWINBURNE UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY**

- Microgravity research
- Pharmaceutical processing

(End user community) e.g. Pharmaceutical, Life Sciences, Optical fibres, Semiconductor industries e.g. Merck, Flawless Photonics

(Improved Sustainability) e.g. new ways to reduce debris (carbon composite/materials industries), philanthropic contributors, space re-entry/situational awareness e.g. New Frontier Technologies, Viasat

(Ground infrastructure and logistics) e.g. production infrastructure and logistics, urban design/architecture e.g. HDR, Aspen Medical

(Enabling) Space infrastructure companies including AI/Cyber, local community engagement, policy and economic frameworks, local governments e.g. Varda, Intuitive Machines, Egress Space, Australasian Centre for Space Governance

The reduced cost of access to the low gravity space environment combined with technological advancements such as AI, have for the first time opened a commercially driven opportunity to manufacture new and high value products routinely and Australia has a head start to be one of the first hubs for this activity.

The aim of the CRC is to grow the domestic ecosystem capable of delivering this new opportunity beginning with Varda's remote capsule return of today to a fully-fledged CBR airport hub-like capability within 10 years.

Driving a sustainable economy based on this access requires a broad ecosystem approach, including product case development, broad technological solutions, sustainability and safe practices and impactful social and community engagement throughout.

We'd like your help to identify further industry stakeholders (from end users to enablers) across the country who could benefit from the matched funding opportunities of the CRC.

Bid lead - ANU Institute for Space, other research areas

Bushfire mitigation

Advanced communication

Space medicine

Regional engagement

National Space
Qualification Network

Climate resilience

For more information, please contact:
Space.CRCBid@anu.edu.au

Invited speaker: Allen (Zhengyu) Wen (ANU)

Talk title: Powering the Australian bioeconomy through plant innovation

Biography

Dr Allen (Zhengyu) Wen is the Head of Plant SynBio Australia-ANU in the Research School of Biology at The Australian National University (ANU). He is a plant molecular biologist with deep expertise in genetic transformation and genome editing, supporting the development of accelerated breeding capabilities across major crop species. Dr Wen's career spans both academia and industry-focused R&D, with previous roles including work at KeyGene (USA) and the International Maize and Wheat Improvement Center (CIMMYT). At CIMMYT, he established a maize gene-editing platform and contributed to the development of elite gene-edited maize lines with strong disease resilience, demonstrating the potential of rapid trait deployment without compromising yield. At ANU, he leads efforts to integrate advanced breeding technologies, automation, and translational support to accelerate innovation across Australia's plant bioeconomy, while also mentoring early-career researchers in modern synthetic biology methods.

Invited speaker: Graham Dorrington (RMIT)

Session introduction to “Engineering life support systems”

Biography

Dr Graham Dorrington is an aeronautical engineer and academic based at RMIT University in Melbourne, Australia. He received his PhD from the University of Cambridge and has worked across aerospace research and teaching in both the UK and Australia. Dr Dorrington is widely known for his pioneering work on lighter-than-air aircraft, including the design and piloting of ultra-light airships developed for low-impact environmental exploration. His airship work was featured in Werner Herzog’s documentary *The White Diamond* (2004), which follows the engineering challenges of aerial rainforest canopy exploration. His broader interests span aerospace design, sustainable flight concepts, and the development of novel platforms for scientific exploration in complex environments.

Invited speaker: Volker Hessel (AU)

Talk title: Digital twins for decision making for vine disease and vertical farm management (“Plants for Space”)

Biography

Professor Volker Hessel is a chemical engineer and researcher in the School of Chemical Engineering at the University of Adelaide, with a career spanning both academic and industrial R&D. Trained originally as a chemist, he has held senior leadership roles in microtechnology and process innovation, including research directorship positions at the Institut für Mikrotechnik Mainz (IMM) in Germany, and professorial appointments at Eindhoven University of Technology in the Netherlands. Professor Hessel is internationally recognised for his contributions to flow chemistry, process intensification, and novel process windows, and is the author or co-author of more than 600 peer-reviewed publications. His work increasingly focuses on sustainable and resilient food and bioproduction systems, including the simulation of space conditions on Earth to develop digital and physical “twins” of plant and food production for future missions. He is a Chief Investigator within Australia’s ARC Centre of Excellence in Plants for Space, bringing a strong systems and translation-oriented approach to the future of bioengineered living systems.

"Digital twins for decision making for vine disease- and vertical farm management ("Plants for Space")".

Volker Hessel

ARC Centre of Excellence in Plants for Space
School of Chemical Engineering
The University of Adelaide

GAPS IN SPACE RESEARCH – HUMAN WELL-BEING

Hoyos, Hessel, Cook, Escriba-Gelonch et al. *Processes* 12, 10 (2024) 2105

ARC CENTRE OF EXCELLENCE PLANTS FOR SPACE, P4S

1st mission

2nd mission

3rd mission

4th mission

This project: Zero-waste plants

This project: On-demand bioresource production

MOLECULAR PLANT SCIENCE

PLANT PHYSIOLOGY

PLANT PHARMA

PLANTS AS BIORESOURCES

CONTROLLED ENV. AG.

SYSTEMS ENGINEERING

FOOD STRUCTURING

FOOD PROCESSING

DIGESTION

SINGLE CELL 'OMICS

GENE EDITING

LAW & POLICY

EDUCATION

OUTREACH

PSYCHOLOGY

SENSORY SCIENCE

**P4S will deliver
fundamental
learnings
& innovations
for Space
and Earth**

Plants

Medicine

Material

law

Foods

Flavour

Recycle

Teams

Goal: Investigate suitability of lunar surface as a growth environment for crops

Objectives: Compare **molecular¹** and **physiological²** differences between Earth and Lunar grown plants.

via ¹sample return and ²remote modelling

LEAF

(2026)

Space Lab[®]

AEA Ignite Project: a Path to Commercial of Our MAGS-DT

AI & Digital Twins: The future of Farming

Posted on Mar 18, 2025 by Marilia Jean Belperio

amazon

constellation technologies CT

Federation University

XMPRO

SERAFINO WINES

AGORA HIGH TECH

PPS PERENNIAL PASTURE SYSTEMS
MAKING PASTURE DO THE DISTANCE

Digital Twins in Agriculture: Orchestration and Applications, M Escribà-Gelonch, V Hessel, Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry 72, 19 (2024)10737-10752.

WHAT IS A DIGITAL TWIN?

- Real-time digital representation of a physical system
- Components: sensors, cloud analytics, AI models
- Functions: **simulate**, **predict**, and **optimise decisions**

Industrial Digital Twin Approach, our Partner Constellation Technologies

DECISION MAKING AS A CENTRAL PART OF DIGITAL TWIN

Deterministic and rule-based: switch points by equations

Governance flow

Probabilistic and context-sensitive: discourse & feedback

Agent: software that is empowered to make decisions and take actions.

Agent commercial success:

Companies like Domino's, Uber, and Salesforce are 30% greater efficient at 25% lower costs.

Agent commercial success in agriculture:

See & Spray software of Blue River Technology company reduced herbicide use by 90%. The AgriTech giant John Deere bought this company.

Decision-Making in Digital Twins, and Opportunities in Agriculture and Food Supply Chain, Mst I Parvin, S Liang, NVD Long, V Hessel In: Digitalisation and Artificial Intelligence in Agritech and Food Supply Chains, S Kumari, VG Venkatesh, J Hernandez, Z El Hathat (Elsevier).

DIGITAL TWIN LOOP FOR DECISION MAKING IN VERTICAL FARM

Digital twin for lettuce growth in six climate zones ('Climate 2050'), S Liang, NVD Long, MI Parvin, M Escribà-Gelonch, S Lantin, V Hessel, Computers and Electronics in Agriculture 238, 110880, 2025. 2. Digital twin modelling of lettuce growth under extreme earth conditions on earth: a very first step to plant growth in outer space, S Liang, NCD Long, S Lantin, M Escribà-Gelonch, V Hessel, Clean Technologies and Environmental Policy, 1-24, 2025.

AGENTS: EXPERTISE DEFINITION@AI

Environment Monitoring Agent **Role:** Master controller for all

environmental parameters including temperature, humidity, CO₂, air circulation, and lighting systems. **Responsibilities**

- Monitor and adjust temperature (18-24°C), humidity (50-70%), CO₂ levels (800-1200 ppm)
- Control LED lighting intensity (200-400 μmol/m²/s) and photoperiod (14-16 hours)
- Manage air circulation and ventilation systems
- Maintain environmental stability within optimal ranges
- Coordinate with other agents for parameter synchronisation

Resource Optimisation Agent

Role: Strategic resource allocation and cost optimization across all operational systems including energy, water, nutrients, and labour.

Responsibilities

- Optimise energy consumption for LED & HVAC
- Manage water usage and recycling
- Coordinate resource procurement and inventory management
- Analyse cost-benefit ratios for operational decisions
- Implement predictive maintenance scheduling

COMPUTER AGENTS AND HUMANOID AGENTS

Environmental Monitoring Agent	Nutrient Management Agent
Intervention Strategist Agent	Resource Optimisation Agent
Compliance Agent	Growth Monitoring Agent

Merged humanoid agent profile, Environmental Monitoring Agent

GOVERNANCE FLOW: DETERMINISM & CONTEXT-SENSITISM

- Industrially coded decision-making flow.
- Opening new business for XMPRO & us

MISSION 3 of P4S: ON-DEMAND BIORESOURCE PRODUCTION

$$f_{team} = W_1(P) - W_2(R_u) - W_3(I_{env}) - W_4(C_{trt}) + W_5(H_{ne})$$

f_{team} f_{MISSION}

- P = Productivity (0-1)
- R_u = Resource use (energy, water, nutrient and leakage) (normalised 0-1)
- C_{trt} = Normalised treatment cost (normalised 0-1, lower is better)
- I_{env} = Environmental impact (normalised 0-1, lower is better)
- H_{ne} = Health Nutrition Effectiveness (0-1)

$$w_1 = 0.30, w_2 = 0.25, w_3 = 0.20, w_4 = 0.15, w_5 = 0.10$$

**Parathyroid hormone (PTH)
Osteoporosis medicine
Ryan Lister, UWA**

Parameter	Actual	max	Term value ($1 - \frac{c}{max}$)	Weighted Contribution ($w_i \times$ value)
Energy (kWh)	3	5	0.40	$0.40 \times 0.40 = 0.16$
Water (L)	3	10	0.70	$0.25 \times 0.70 = 0.175$
Nitrogen (g)	0.7	1.0	0.30	$0.20 \times 0.30 = 0.06$
Leakage (L)	0.05	0.15	0.60	$0.15 \times 0.60 = 0.09$

Resources

Total resource score = $0.16 + 0.14 + 0.06 + 0.12 = 0.485$

Serum Ca concentration (minimum)	Serum Ca concentration (maximum)
8.6 mg/dL	10.3 mg/dL
Below 8.5 mg/dL (2.12 mmol/L)- hypercalcemia	Delivery of Ca (conc) is enough for heavy osteoporosis

$$H_{ne} = \frac{\text{Serum Ca (from hormone)} - 8.6}{10.3 - 8.6} = 0.53$$

Patient health

Environment

Minimum	Maximum
0.1 g of CO ₂ e	250 g CO ₂ e

$$I_{ev} = \frac{\text{CO}_2 \text{ emission per tomato}}{\text{Maximum benchmark emission}} = 0.0004$$

TEAM FUNCTION FOR GRAPE DISEASE MANAGEMENT

$$f_{team} = w1(D_{prev}) - w2(C_{int}) + w3(Q_{grp}) - w4(EI)$$

D_{prev} = Disease prevention effectiveness (0-1)

C_{int} = Cost of intervention (normalized 0-1, lower is better)

Q_{grp} = Grape quality preservation (0-1)

EI = Environmental impact (composite index 0-1)

Here, $w1 = 0.30$, $w2 = 0.25$, $w3 = 0.25$, $w4 = 0.20$.

TEAM FUNCTION EXPERTISE GAINED AT VINE DISEASES

FUNGICIDES TEAM FUNCTION DPE = Disease Prevention Effectiveness YPP = Yield Preservation Percentage TC = Treatment Cost EI = Environmental Impact RT = Relative Thickness RB = Relative Brix RA = Relative Acidity CS = Composite Score Ft(eff) = fteam effectiveness

Treatment	DPE	nYPP	nTC	nEI	nRT	nRB	nRA	CS	ft(eff) (%)
Sulfur	0.789	0.293	1	0	1	0.207	1	0.736	31.24
Fosetyl-Al	0.604	0.257	0.442	1	0.371	0	0.640	0.337	4.83
K-Bicarbonate	0.961	0.140	0	0.003	0.371	0.075	0.675	0.374	52.71
Trichoderma	0.755	0	1	0.182	0	0.628	0	0.209	0.50
Fenhaximid	0.437	1	0.535	0.402	0.651	1	0.807	0.819	47.04

Parameter	Botrytis Untreated	Fenhaximid Treated
Relative °Brix	0.90	0.99
Relative Titratable Acidity (TA)	1.10	1.02
Relative Berry Thickness	0.85	0.98

Josephine Tanu, UWA

DISEASE PREDICTION: CNN MODEL WITH ONLINE DATASET (CNN-KMeans Hybrid Disease Detection and Severity Estimation Model)

Disease detection and severity estimation

Accuracy analysis using classification metrics

DISEASE DETECTION, CONFIDENCE AND SEVERITY%

Analysed data	Test image	Fit: Black Measles %	Fit :Black Rot %	Fit: Healthy leaf %	Fit: Leaf Blight %	Disease prediction	Confidence %	Image after masking	Disease severity %
Image 1		18.4							
Image 2		8.055							
Image 3		23.484							
Image 4		37.218							
Image 5		16.059							
Image 6		11.104							
Image 7		20.271							
Image 8		15.700							
Image 9		13.25							

RESULTS FROM OUR DEVELOPED CNN MODEL

Grape Leaf Disease Image Dataset

Includes blackrot, blackmeasles, leafblight, healthy

For training: totally 7222 images

For testing: totally 1805 images

Performance evaluation of the model

Accuracy: 0.9989

MSE : 0.000388

RMSE : 0.019707

R2 : 0.997927

Training & Validation Accuracy

Training & Validation Loss

CNN model predicted disease detection

leaf_id	x0	y0	x1	y1	predicted_label	top_prob_%	has_disease	Grape__Black_rot	Grape__Esca_(Black_Measles)	Grape__Leaf_blight_(Isariopsis_Leaf_Spot)	Grape__healthy
1	628	0	808	120	Grape__Esca_(Black_Measles)	78.92	1	1.66	78.92	18.63	0.79

FABA BEAN GROWTH UNDER LUNAR GRAVITY

Faba beans grow on 'moon dust' almost as good as on fertile soil

Faba beans on highland 'moon dust' are as stable as on soil when exposed to cosmic (gamma) rays

SLS: Sandy loam soil

LHS-1: Lunar highland regolith ('moon dust')

LMS-1: Lunar lowland regolith

Microgravity machine (Airbus) with mini-phytotron (greenhouse)

Brewer, David, Hessel et al., Nature

Microgravity **11** (2025) 28

SPACECRAFT REPLICA & BIOPHILIC RENDERING

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

THE UNIVERSITY
of ADELAIDE

School of Chemical Engineering

THANK YOU! QUESTIONS?

- 1) Digital twin for lettuce growth in six climate zones ('Climate 2050'), S Liang, NVD Long, M Parvin, M Escrivà-Gelonch, S Lantin, V Hessel, *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture* 238, 110880, 2025. DOI: 10.1016/J.COMPAG.2025.110880
- 2) Digital twin modelling of lettuce growth under extreme earth conditions on earth: a very first step to plant growth in outer space, S Liang, NVD Long, S Lantin, M Escrivà-Gelonch, V Hessel, *Clean Technologies and Environmental Policy*, 1-24, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10098-025-03293-8>
- 3) Digital twins in agriculture: orchestration and applications, M Escrivà-Gelonch, S Liang, P van Schalkwyk, I Fisk, NVD Long, ..., *Journal of agricultural and food chemistry* 72 (19), 10737-10752, 2024. doi: 10.1021/acs.jafc.4c01934 69 citations
- 4) Application of Machine Learning and Digital Twin in Smart Farming for Space and Extreme Environments, NVD Long, S Liang, M Escrivà-Gelonch, V Hessel, In: De Paolis, L.T., Arpaia, P., Sacco, M. (eds) *Extended Reality. XR Salento 2025. Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, vol 15740. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-97772-5_5
- 5) Digital Twins for Agriculture, with Space Vantage Outlook, Mst I Parvin, S Liang, NVD Long, M Escrivà-Gelonch, Volker Hessel, In: *Foundations of Digital Twins (Advances in Digital Twin Computing and Sensor Networks)*, Tuan Anh Nguyen, Jun Cai, Marjan Kuchaki Rafsanjani, ISBN-13 : 978-0443438974, DOI: soon. Elsevier
- 6) Decision-Making in Digital Twins, and Opportunities in Agriculture and Food Supply Chain, Mst Irin Parvin, S Liang, NVD Long, V Hessel, In: *Digitalisation and Artificial Intelligence in Agritech and Food Supply Chains*, Sneha Kumari, V.G. Venkatesh, Jorge Hernandez, Zakaria El Hathat, DOI: soon. Springer Nature
- 7) Conferences: Off-Earth Mining Forum (OEMS), Sydney; Australian Space Research Conference 2025, Melbourne
P4S Annual Conference 2025, Gold Coast
- 8) Selected after application for: 10th EMBL Australia PhD Course (2025), Monash University, Melbourne

Invited speaker: William E. Hollier (EnGen Institute)

Talk title: Context dependence of survival and life support systems

Biography

William E. Hollier is the Director and Research Lead of the EnGen Institute, where he works on advanced systems engineering approaches to survival, resilience, and life-support systems. Trained originally in physics at Monash University, he has built a career spanning defence research, computing, and engineering design, with roles including experimental work at the Royal Australian Navy Research Laboratories and research at CSIRO. Over decades, he has led technical innovation across software systems, automation, and generative engineering methods, including early contributions to operating system design and engineering design automation. His work at EnGen Institute is focused on developing sustainable, self-repairing technological systems for extreme environments, drawing on ideas from generative design and self-replicating system theory to inform how complex infrastructures can be built, maintained, and scaled under constraints. At the Bioengineered Living Systems Workshop, he presented on the context dependence of survival and life-support systems.

Context Dependence of Survival and Life Support Systems

ENGEN

William E. Hollier
Director, EnGen Institute

Biomass Production System

NASA Biomass Production System 1985 - 2001

Bioengineered Living Systems Workshop, Mt Stromlo Observatory, ANU, Dec 4th & 5th 2025

Context Dependence of Survival and Life Support Systems

SURVIVAL SYSTEMS

Protective Containment System with Life-Support Systems within

The Earth's magnetic field, gravity, atmosphere & 'Goldilocks' orbit protect us from hazards such as cosmic radiation. Earth's Biosphere provides the life support conditions essential to life. Conditions we must take with us into space and the deep sea.

A spacestation, spaceship, spacebase or spacesuit is a survival system having life support systems within. The same is true of a submarine or diving suit.

Context Dependence of Survival and Life Support Systems

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All survival systems have -

- a protective containment enclosure

Context Dependence of Survival and Life Support Systems

SURVIVAL SYSTEMS

Protective Containment System with Life-Support Systems within

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A spacestation, spaceship, spacebase or spacesuit is a survival system having life support systems within. The same is true of a submarine or diving suit.

All survival systems have -

- a protective containment enclosure, and
- life-support system, that maintains an internal environment with the conditions necessary for life.

This is also true of a humicrib or womb – both are protective containment environments with life support systems within. These are systemic characteristics.

Bioengineered Living Systems Workshop, Mt Stromlo Observatory, ANU, Dec 4th & 5th 2025

Context Dependence of Survival and Life Support Systems

TO THE INSTITUTIONAL RESEARCH DIRECTOR -

What this talk is about - its objective and purpose is –

- Planning ahead so research results, including commercialization, occur when needed, not decades out-of-date. Research intended to be used.
- Developing in demand systems, not too late – or an ‘also ran’ result.
- New technology, not reiterations of decades old tech.
- Realistic timeframes for development, deployment, proof of function/reliability.
- The advantage of just getting started – free choice!
So, ask yourself -

Are We Researching a Dead-end Context?

- is it already or soon superseded – or essential to future space?
- Where is it all headed? to the Moon , Mars ... Deep space – **How!**
- What will the real context(s) of Bioengineered Living Systems be?
- What works on the Moon, may not on Mars, or in long-duration Deep space.
- Will your research produce a sole supplier situation with lots of interested space agencies, collaborators and investors – or a forgettable ‘also ran’?

Context Dependence of Survival and Life Support Systems

Viability of Mars Soil Agriculture?

'The Martian' movie is fantasy! The facts are -

Mars soil high salinity, perchlorates, silica dust toxicity, low nutrients; extreme temperature fluctuations, low atmospheric pressure, less sunlight, and intense, planet-engulfing dust storms that block light and can damage equipment.

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Context Dependence of Survival and Life Support Systems

Viability of Lunar Soil Agriculture?

Lunar soil sharp/abrasive, toxic, electrostatic dust and adhesion (lungs/cardio); no atmosphere, 28-day day/night cycle, extreme temperature fluctuation, high radiation; no plant nutrients – no nitrogen or organic matter, low bio availability.

- University of Arizona - Lunar Greenhouse (2010)
- ISS Veggi (2014) & Advance Plant Habitat (2017)

Figure 1

Advanced Plant Habitat

Context Dependence of Survival and Life Support Systems

Improving Vertical Farming

So, you will most likely be considering a plant growth system as in Vertical Farming.

Vertical Farming has proved commercially unviable despite USD 9.63 billion invested.

Not because of the capital cost or power cost but labour cost (specialist expertise and manpower).

Vertical Farming is tending towards further automation, sensors, robotics and AI, as it needs to be more sophisticated.

What is required (ie. research objectives) is –

- completely automated, diet-based, **polyculture**.
- Extremely reliable, fool-proof CEA, with **precise scheduled growing & harvesting**
- **Total 100% recyclability** of all plants, media and nutrients.

But in what context?

Vertical Farming Monoculture

Context Dependence of Survival and Life Support Systems

Context: First - how relevant for in-space food production are –

- low/no gravity,
- radiation effects,
- temperature extremes,
- low pressure – partial atmosphere, and
- breeding plants for these conditions?

EnGen maintains –

Soon, the answer will be none.

As none of these are critical or even important priorities.

Because the context of in-space CEA is about to change.

Bioengineered Living Systems will still be essential, but the context and research priorities will change.

Let me explain –

Context Dependence of Survival and Life Support Systems

Rotating Spacebases are Survival Systems with 'Artificial Gravity'

SpaceX's tethered or assembled rotating spacebases will have artificial gravity – equal to Moon (0.17G), Mars (0.38G) or Earth (1G) gravity

- a 20m carbon fibre tether rotating at 3 RPM = 0.38 G = Mars Gravity.
- Hydrogen compounds (water and/or methane fuel) are radiation shielding.
- Starship provides far more room and payload capacity – for larger habitats.

Illustration depicting a SpaceX Crew Dragon spacecraft tethered to a Falcon 9 second stage which could be spun up (in direction of down arrow) to test centrifugal force artificial gravity. Credit: Joe Carroll

Centripetal force $FC = m \cdot r \cdot \omega^2$, so $g = r \cdot \omega^2 = (g/1) \cdot (1 \text{ rev./sec})^2 = 60 / 2 \text{ RPM}$

To avoid nausea, RPM should be no more than 5.5 RPM, which at 64m dia. produces 1.08 G. However, a lower (≤ 2.5) RPM and/or larger diameter would be more comfortable.

[A Block 3 Starship is 61 m high, with 9m diameter. A tethered pair has ≥ 122 m dia.]

Gravity Starship: SpaceX is already designing a rotating spacestation they call the Gravity Starship - e.g. joining rotating starships, then using active magnetic bearings, and a non-rotating central docking hub with solar array supports.

Context Dependence of Survival and Life Support Systems

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Context Dependence of Survival and Life Support Systems

Rotating Spacebases with 'Artificial' Gravity

Starships stainless steel construction suits rotating space stations – it resists radiation, micrometeor strikes and temperature swings from +120 C to -150 C

Soviet Bion 3 satellite (1975) included a centrifuge to test plant growth under different 'artificial' gravity.

Hydrogen-Rich Fuel & Water

absorb radiation and can be stored surrounding living quarters. NASA, SpaceX, United Launch Alliance (ULA) and Blue Origin already use concentric tanks and divided tanks.

Context Dependence of Survival and Life Support Systems

Availability of Construction Materials

In-space refuelling is required for a Starship Lunar Return Mission and for Starship Mars Missions. Expendable Tanker Starships avoid the weight & cost of the re-entry heatshield, grid flaps & legs to increase payload, then are orbiting space junk.

[https://www.youtube.com/watch?](https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=2Zygknvpw8A&t=52s)

[v=2Zygknvpw8A&t=52s](https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=2Zygknvpw8A&t=52s)

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5lmB4yerrlA>

These 'free' tankers can be used to construct SpaceX's proposed Rotating Spacestation.

In-space Construction: NASA has several current programs of in-space assembly & manufacturing.

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An Artificial-Gravity Space-Settlement Ground-Analogue Design Concept

Gregory A. Dorais¹
NASA Ames Research Center, Moffett Field, CA, 94035

<https://ntrs.nasa.gov/citations/20160013852>
Extended-Stay Hyper Gravity Facility

Also recently proposed is a Toroidal Rotating Lunar Spacebase - rotating on Magnetic Bearings, possibly within a Lunar Tunnel.

Context Dependence of Survival and Life Support Systems

High Impact of Space on Humans:

After 6 months in microgravity astronaut's loose up to 20% of muscle mass, 1% of bone density per month, the heart reshapes, the brain's fluid balance changes, vision permanently distorts and trace lunar dust causes lung damage, so **artificial gravity is mandatory to live in space.** Humans living long-term on the Moon or Mars will be so adapted to low gravity, if they survive, they **will be unable to return to Earth.** Within one generation there will be three human races. **None of this occurs within a 1G, STP‡ radiation shielded, rotating spacestation or spacebase - utilizing telepresence to planetary robotics. *** A similar situation existed for oil rig deep divers who lived in deep habitats, as it took too long to decompress and hence operate from the ship. *

Oil rig divers were replaced by teleoperated robotic AUVs.

‡ STP (Standard Temperature and Pressure) 20°C at 1 atm

* [From 2000-2005 I researched at RMIT I³]

* [After graduating in Physics, I joined the Underwater Research Group at RANRL.]

Context Dependence of Survival and Life Support Systems

In-Space Teleoperated Robotics :

1. Lunar Internet - high performance via Starlink
2. Tesla's 'Optimus Gen 3' humanoid robots
3. Optimus is supported by 'Grok AI' connection

Telepresence from Lunar/Mars Orbit:

- by astronauts in orbiting rotating space stations;
- solves the communications latency problem.
- Optimus-Grok connection via Lunar Net

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OK it's possible, but - Why should this happen?

Human - Mission Duration Limits

- currently a return Mars mission is near the human limit
eg. human needs - limit nuclear submarine mission duration
- Stress - of a small crew, in a small space, for long periods
- **Space travel in a 1G, STP, radiation shielded spacestation with Bioregenerative Life Support System Earth analogue) and larger community**
these problems

Chances of this happening?

Economics of SpaceX vs NASA

- NASA's SLS costs \$4.1B per launch; Starship \$10M per launch
- the ISS cost \$US 150B to build; annual maintenance \$150m.
- one ISS Mission cost \$71m per person x 3 = \$213m
- SpaceX could deploy a large orbital space station for less than one ISS mission.
- SpaceX has commenced design of a rotating spacestation to be deployed in the 2030s – to orbit the Moon, Mars, Earth - be stationed at Lagrange points, or possibly as a spaceship.
- the ISS is due for decommissioning in 2030.

Context Dependence of Survival and Life Support Systems

Bioregenerative Life Support System

Bioregenerative Life Support Systems (BLSS)

- Bioregenerative Systems are a current research frontier of NASA, ESA, JAXA, etc
- BLSS are closed-loop ecosystems that support astronauts, for years, beyond resupply lines, that
- combine plants, algae and other species in sub-habitats to recycle air, water, and food naturally.
- NASA will start using **Ohalo III** modular cropping growth chambers in space in 2026

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Context Dependence of Survival and Life Support Systems Aquaculture and Aquaponics in Space

TABLE 3 | Studies of aquaculture fish as models for sensory motor, reflex experiments and trophic chain demonstrations in low orbit missions. References to major missions are noted with numbers in brackets: [12] Mori, 1994 [13] Sebastian, 2001 [14] Anken, 2016.

Year	Fish species	Mission	Low orbit station	Duration	Fish stage	Embryos	Study aim
1992	Common carp <i>Cyprinus carpio</i>	STS-47 ^[12] <i>Endeavour</i>	Space Lab-J ML2	8 days	2 carp (263–270 g)	–	Sensory motor experiment
1993	Tilapia <i>O. mossambicus</i>	STS-55 ^[13] <i>Columbia</i>	Space Lab D-2	9 days	Larvae (post-hatching)	–	Vestibuloocular reflex test
1997	Tilapia <i>O. mossambicus</i>	STS-84 ^[13] <i>Atlantis</i>	MIR SMM-06	10 days	Larvae (post-hatching)	–	Vestibuloocular reflex test–video
2007	Tilapia <i>O. mossambicus</i>	Soyuz-U ^[14]	Foton M3	12 days	26 larvae (12 mm)	–	Video–vestibular organ–enzymatic activity
2013	Tilapia <i>O. mossambicus</i>	Soyuz 2 1a	BION-M1	30 days	All fish died	–	Equipment failure

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Aquaponics

Aquaponics combines hydroponics and aquaculture in a closed loop system in which fish waste (urea) is converted into plant fertilizer (nitrates) by micro-organisms. This is a step towards BLSS and towards a balanced healthy diet.

The hydroponic, aquaculture and micro-organism systems can be isolated if disease breaks out.

Aquaponics Schematic

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<p>Concept A 3D array of bioengineered living cells deposits materials, both biological and inorganic, that are bound into nonliving, microstructured finished products.</p> <p>Potential applications:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • high-fidelity, low-overhead reproduction of existing biomaterials (food, wood, bone) • flexible, just-in-time manufacturing and repair in on- and off-Earth environments • rapid design and production of new, synthetic biomaterials • opens up new frontiers in space missions, advanced manufacturing, and material science 	<p>Study Approach</p> <p>Proof-of-concept:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Optimize cell dispensing system for digitized materials • Engineer <i>S. cerevisiae</i> cells to secrete material components • Show successful cell secretion and material separation • Produce a 2-material array from a digitized template <p>Feasibility/Benefit Study</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Determine effect of printing parameters on material yield • Determine effect of printing parameters on material structure • Identify key procedural parameters of technique • Use results to determine potential upmass reduction of long-term Mars habitat
<p>Benefits</p> <p>Of the concept:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • drastically reduces upmass requirements of many current space missions • greatly multiplies potential of off-planet in situ resource utilization • enables new class of space missions currently precluded by material transport needs • vast potential for exploration of novel, synthetic biomaterials and biocomposites <p>Of this study:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • given current progress, potential of approach can be established or dismissed in single year • technology moved from TRL 2 to 3 	<div data-bbox="486 907 1189 1377" style="text-align: center;"> </div> <p>Evaluation Notes</p> <div data-bbox="1061 1384 1540 1619" style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px;"> <p style="text-align: right; font-size: small;">NIAC 2013 Phase I Final Report</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Biomaterials out of thin air: <i>in situ</i>, on-demand printing of advanced biocomposites</p> <p style="text-align: center; font-size: small;">A New Materials Design and Production Technique using 3D-Printed Arrays of Bioengineered Cells</p> <p style="text-align: center; font-size: x-small;">Diana Gentry, NASA Ames Research Center (Co-I.) (diana.gentry@nasa.gov) Ashley Micks, Stanford University (aemixx@stanford.edu) Lynn Rothschild, NASA Ames Research Center (PI.) (lynn.j.rothschild@nasa.gov)</p> <p style="text-align: right; font-size: x-small;">June 3, 2014</p> </div>

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Context Dependence of Survival and Life Support Systems

SURVIVAL SYSTEM REGENERATION

As all equipment will at some time break or wear out. For the long duration 'Far from Earth' capability required for space voyaging and colonization, survival systems (spacecraft, all equipment & BLSS) **must have the capability to regenerate** (repair or recycle & remake) **both their life support systems and their entire technological systems, while still operating.**

NASA already has early studies investigating self-repairing technologies for Moon to Mars missions consisting of external and internal robotics; and aspires to develop self-replicating technologies.

This is best achieved **where both inorganic and organic systems can regenerate, not only as independent tech-cycles and eco-cycles but also having a coupling between cycles.**

For example -

Context Dependence of Survival and Life Support Systems

Bio-based biodegradable recyclable plastics

Recent studies have described the production of bioplastics by using cyanobacteria blooms that use sunlight to produce chemicals through photosynthesis.

Evocative, a New York-based company, has used mycelium – vegetative fungal extensions that give rise to mushrooms – to make plastic-like materials for biodegradable packaging and tiling.

Poly-lactic acid (PLA) is a thermoplastic aliphatic polyester obtained by polymerizing lactic acid from renewable resources, such as corn starch, tapioca roots, chips or starch, etc.

3D Printers with PLA filament recycling are now available and PLA is also biodegradable at 60°C+O₂+microorganisms.

Context Dependence of Survival and Life Support Systems

OK, the eco-cycle can self-replicate and couple to the Tech-cycle, but how does the Tech-cycle regenerate (ie. self-replicate) itself?

NASA's Current Technology Roadmap (current until 2036)

2015 NASA Technology Roadmaps
TA 4: Robotics and Autonomous Systems

July 2015

TA 4.7.1 Modularity, Commonality, and Interfaces

Modular, self-reconfigurable robotic technologies are applicable to machines with changing morphology. Their promise of high versatility and robustness could have significant value in enabling field replacement of failed components, leading to self-adaptable and self-repair systems.

Modular interfaces, which may include mechanical, electrical, fluid, and pneumatic interfaces, form the basis for robotic assembly and servicing. Examples include tool change-out on robotic arms for rovers or for in-space robotic assembly and servicing. Tools and end-effectors developed in a modular manner have a reduced logistics footprint over dedicated arms with specialized tools. These interfaces also allow new space operations and architectures to be realized. One example is on-orbit re-fueling and servicing, which has the potential to change space mission architectures.

Modular and common interfaces are also the building blocks for reconfigurable and self-assembling, and perhaps even self-replicating, robotic systems. Such system design allows deployed systems to respond to changing needs and system failures through in-situ reconfiguration of mechanical, electrical, and computing assets.

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NASA is assuming reconfigurable modular robotics, which can reconfigure assemblies of modules (ie. external action), not an automaton able to construct a duplicate of itself (ie. internal action) as described by John von Neumann in his 'Theory of Self-Reproducing Automata' – hence the cautious 'perhaps even' as this requires robotics capable of internal action. NASA's AASM and later studies have sought but failed to define John von Neumann's 'Universal Constructor'. This quandary has been solved by the author via 'Generative Construction'. Universal Construction is impossible and akin to perpetual motion.

Context Dependence of Survival and Life Support Systems

Current NASA expertise in self-assembling and self-repairing structures -

NASA Ames Robotics Automation and Assembly Webinar

[Register for Event](#)

About the Event

When: Wed, 12/3/2025 at 1:00 PM (Eastern Time)

If you're using Mozilla Firefox and have issues with the registration form, please try disabling extensions or use a different browser.

Explore how NASA Ames Research Center is bringing autonomous structural assembly to life with a suite of robotics technologies now available for licensing. This webinar will highlight three innovations: a mobile bipedal robot system that can carry, position, and assemble lightweight lattice modules into large-scale structures; a reversible fastener designed for high-strength, robot-friendly connections; and a novel modular method for building cuboctahedron lattice materials.

Together, these technologies allow robots to construct, monitor, and even repair

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'self'-repair & 'self'-replication study

ENGINEERED GENERATION OF

ENGINEERED ENVIRONMENTS

Self-assembling
Self-repairing &
Self-replicating
Structure Design
and Evolution
- including for
Survival Systems

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Context Dependence of Survival and Life Support Systems

NASA's SpaceSeed Concept

NASA's AASM Study progressed beyond just self-replication to analysis of an engineering systems able to develop from a seed.

This space 'Seed' concept is a 100-ton Lunar Lander*, that on landing begins, via its teleoperated initial robotics, to unpack, assemble and deploy a 120m diameter initial lunar facility.

First, it deploys an initial solar array to provide power, then solar powered robots having large parabolic mirrors, to produce 'hardstand' paving via sintering lunar regolith (soil). Then it deploys its initial machinery onto the hardstand before commencing mining.

AASM p. 190

"The initial system should be able to successfully develop into an expanded machine system capable of conducting all functions necessary for autonomous replication, growth, and automated production and manufacturing."

NASA's 1980 AASM Study

NASA AASM diagram

The SpaceSeed is something like an organic seed with seed coat, embryo and endosperm. Like a plant, the SpaceSeed has an initial 'establishment' (unpack and initial viability) phase, then growth, production and replication phases.

* SpaceX's Starship HLS, due to land on the Moon in 2026, has 100-ton payload

Context Dependence of Survival and Life Support Systems

NASA's 1980 AASM Study specified -

Automata Development Milestones

Phase 1: Design and construct on Earth a system which -

1. when **supplied only with parts and subassemblies**, can duplicate itself
2. can duplicate itself, and **in addition produce some useful product**
3. when **supplied only with feedstock**, can duplicate itself
4. when **supplied with raw materials only**, can duplicate itself,
5. and **is an Automated, Programmable, Multiproduct Replicating (APMR) system**.

Phase 2: Then using only lunar materials and processes possible in the lunar environment, design and construct on Earth a system which

6. **can duplicate itself from lunar raw materials**,
7. **is an initial automatic "seed" system**, within a lunar lander, which if placed on the lunar surface – could unpack itself and **develop into an APMR system in the lunar environment**
8. could develop and augment itself so as to **become a general-product factory**.
9. design and construct a seed which can, **in an arbitrary planetary environment, develop into a general-product factory**.

Self-Duplication by assembly from –

1. Parts Robot (+ Products), then
2. Feedstock Parts Robot, then
3. Mined Ore Processed Ore
Feedstock Parts Robot.

launch this Lander to the Moon

launch this Lander to Mars

Context Dependence of Survival and Life Support Systems

Self-Replication Research

Development since NASA's AASM study

NASA's AASM and later studies have sought but failed to define John von Neumann's 'Universal Constructor'. This quandary has been solved by the author via 'Generative Construction'. Universal Construction is impossible and akin to perpetual motion.

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Invited speaker: Tom Loan (ANU)

Talk title: Biological surface adhesion

Biography

Dr Tom Loan studied chemistry at the University of Canterbury, New Zealand, before moving to the Australian National University to complete a PhD. Afterwards, he spent five years at the CSIRO developing food and feed additives using microbes and synthetic biology. He is now applying that expertise to biomining, with particular interests in how microbes can be engineered to create new materials and survive in extreme environments.

Invited speaker: Ming-Dao Chia (ANU)

Talk title: Technical challenges in adapting plant phenotyping to space platforms

Biography

Ming-dao Chia is a Technical Officer with the Borevitz Lab at The Australian National University (ANU) and the Australian Plant Phenomics Facility (ANU node). His work sits at the intersection of plant genomics, phenotyping infrastructure, and rapid prototyping, supporting research aimed at understanding plant performance and climate adaptation. He designs and 3D-prints custom laboratory equipment, conducts nanopore DNA sequencing, and develops scripts and utilities to streamline experimental workflows and data analysis. His technical interests extend to applications in plant molecular farming and urban indoor agriculture, as well as the use of remotely piloted aircraft for science communication and ecological research. At the Bioengineered Living Systems Workshop, he presented on technical challenges and opportunities in adapting plant phenotyping tools for space-relevant environments, including constraints on sample size, sensor resolution, and trait measurement accuracy.

Technical challenges in adapting plant phenotyping to space platforms

Ming Chia – APPN-ANU

- Evaluation of phenotypic traits for ALEPH
- Experimental work with Natalie de Santis (Byrt group ANU)
- Lichens from Dr Cecile Guiedan (CSIRO)
- Instruments from APPN-ANU

DRY

subjects

instruments

RGB

Gas exchange

Hyperspectral

Fluorescence

challenges

1. Low sample counts require new experimental design and analysis

2. Reduced resolution with space sensors needs new methodologies

-1	1
1	-1

$ExG = 0$

0	1
1	0

$ExG = 0.5$

3. Slight increases in accuracy may require complete overhauls in measurement

Invited speaker: Shagufta Iqbal (ANU)

Talk title: Membrane technology in space

Biography

Dr Shagufta Iqbal is a post-doctoral fellow at the Australian National University. She works in both fundamental and applied biochemistry. Her research focuses on membrane proteins and their biochemical interactions, particularly in relation to transport processes in cells. She carries technical expertise, particularly in the areas of membrane protein purification, biochemical characterisation, reconstitution into model membranes, and functional assays. This expertise helps replicate the transport processes from living organisms into biomimetics through biotechnology.

Invited speaker: Sharon Robinson (UOW)

Panel discussion: Knowledge gaps we need to fill

Biography

Distinguished Professor Sharon Robinson AM is a climate change biologist at the University of Wollongong and a 2024 Australian Laureate Fellow. She is Deputy Director of Science Implementation for the Australian Research Council Special Research Initiative, Securing Antarctica's Environmental Future, and has led pioneering research on Antarctic vegetation across more than fifteen expeditions to the continent. Her work focuses on understanding how Antarctic plants and cryptogams respond to environmental change, using approaches that span molecular physiology through to ecosystem-scale monitoring. Professor Robinson is the custodian for Antarctica's State of the Environment Indicator on vegetation and is deeply committed to conserving Antarctic biodiversity. Beyond research, she contributes to international science leadership through roles including the UN Environment Programme Environmental Effects Assessment Panel and as a subject editor for Global Change Biology. Her work continues to shape how we measure, interpret, and respond to ecological change in one of Earth's most extreme environments.

